

Towards a Relational Type of Systematicity in Scoping Reviews: Purposeful Sampling and Diffractive Reading Applied to the Field of Human Enhancement

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Abstract

Human enhancement has drawn considerable scientific and public attention in recent decades. It is generally understood as the integration of human and technology to improve human abilities. However, this apparently consensual definition breaks down upon closer examination: many articles mention human enhancement without defining it, or use divergent definitions. Related terms such as "human augmentation" are frequently used interchangeably, and categories of enhancement technologies are numerous and diverse. To address this conceptual ambiguity, this paper presents a scoping review aimed at creating a typology of human enhancement. Our approach challenges the often linear and exhaustive ways of sampling in reviews and questions the signification usually assigned to "systematicity" in systematic reviews, proposing instead the concept of "relational systematicity". The review uses purposeful sampling of peer-reviewed literature across disciplines. Inclusion criteria focus on articles proposing elements of classification of human enhancement. They are collected and diffractively analyzed (Sauzet, 2021) with attention to their definitional assumptions and classification logic, until a working typology is formed. Our goal is twofold: (1) to propose a conceptualization of human enhancement, and (2) to illustrate how purposeful sampling and diffractive reading can be applied in literature reviews to support a more relational way of conducting reviews systematically. The typology will offer researchers a practical tool to categorize technologies not only by technical characteristics, but also by intended purpose and real-world applications. Ultimately, this work lays the groundwork for further analysis of the societal implications of human enhancement, and proposes an alternative relational way to conduct systematic reviews.

Keywords

Human enhancement, typology, purposeful sampling, diffractive reading, feminist new materialisms, systematic reviews, relational systematicity

1. Introduction: Toward a New Form of Literature Review

At times it can be challenging for a young PhD student to know what is expected from them. They are told "at the end of your first year, you must have conducted a systematic review". But what does that exactly mean, being systematic? Is it the idea of conducting the same steps, in the same order, no matter what topic is investigated? Does it refer to the comprehensiveness of the search terms, the databases searched, the articles included? Or is it related to transparency of choices made in the search strategy, the selection process, the quality assessment. How is systematicity linked to the rigor of the analysis process used to synthesize evidence? Even well conducted reviews have been critiqued for the biases that they transmit in deciding on in- and exclusion criteria, how these decisions influence all other steps in the review process but are seldom discussed. This points toward a lack of critical reflection exercised over the knowledge they accumulate and legitimize (Van Even, 2023).

In this paper, we problematize the dominant interpretation of "systematicity" in literature reviews. We unbox the rationalism that is inherent to most systematic reviews and question the positivistic imperatives of standardization and comprehensiveness that are attached to the notion of systematicity. Instead, we consider how the term systematicity could be given other meanings to better answer the needs of diverse fields. We argue that a standardized review approach and a comprehensive search of the

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literature do not always provide results of the best quality, especially in fields such as socio-behavioral sciences where topics of investigation are often complex, relational and therefore not always reducible to a set of narrowly defined concepts. This is particularly the case in emergent fields (Coemans et al., 2015). This calls for a more critical, fluid review that does not simply aim for syntheses of evidence that further fragmentize scientific knowledge but instead builds bridges across disciplines in an effort to create a common lexicon about complex reality under investigation.

We approach this tension by proposing another interpretation of what systematicity means in literature reviews; more precisely, we explore what the concept *relational systematicity* has to offer when reviewing the interdisciplinary literature on human enhancement. We thereby deliberately seek to move away from positivistic assumptions underlying systematic reviews. We use the concept “relational systematicity” to contrast the usual coherence, linearity, objectivity and generality of systematic reviews with a more fluid, processual, situated and entangled method of literature reviews. We further investigate how such review method inspires us to approach scoping reviews on emerging topics differently and consequently helps us to produce new types of classification systems, models, maps or cartographies. Our research question is, “What is the impact of applying relational systematicity to a review and how does it influence the presentation of the findings on the evidence investigated?” In addition, we will explore how a diffractive approach of reading primary studies to make sense of human enhancement practices and discourses might generate alternative, non-binary typologies that account for the intra-action of bodies, technologies, and environments.

We identify human enhancement as an emergent field where little conceptual consensus exists and, as such, as a pertinent use-case for this relational review method. The broader research project in which this paper is inscribed seeks to understand the societal implications of the phenomenon human enhancement, that is, the integration of human and technology to improve human abilities. A preliminar examination of existing definitions and categorizations of this concept reveals, on the one hand, their scarcity, and on the other, the absence of consensus among them. In most studies, the concept human enhancement is ill-described. Definitions also vary depending on the discipline in which they are situated. For example, in computer science, the focus lies on the technological methods used to enhance human abilities¹. In bioethics on the other hand, the subjective experience of enhancement is central². In addition, the concepts “human augmentation” and “human enhancement” are often used interchangeably. Lastly, the criteria employed to differentiate among various forms of human enhancement are numerous, and even when referring to the same factor, they do not consistently employ the same terminology. Besides, we identified the lack of a sociological attempt to develop a framework to understand the topic (Le Dévédec and Guis, 2013), and we argue that a sociological characterization of human enhancement could serve as basis for further empirical investigations into its societal implications.

The specific objective of this study is twofold. Firstly, we aim to purposefully scope the literature for existing definitions and classifications related to the concept human enhancement and human augmentation to produce a workable typology that takes into account relationality as a sociological concept enabling us to account for the societal implications of human enhancement. At the same time, we seek to critically examine systematic reviews as a process, with the aim of making these studies – among the most widely read by both the public and policy-makers, and thus highly influential in shaping public perceptions on certain topics – more ethically grounded (Suri, 2011).

¹For example, Raisamo et al. define human augmentation as follows: "Human augmentation is an interdisciplinary field that addresses methods, technologies and their applications for enhancing sensing, action and/or cognitive abilities of a human. This is achieved through sensing and actuation technologies, fusion and fission of information, and artificial intelligence (AI) methods." (Raisamo et al., 2019)

²See Menuz et al.: “We propose a definition of human enhancement where each individual has to determine for herself/himself, based on her/his personal optimum state, whether the outcome of a given technological intervention can be described as human enhancement or not.” (Menuz et al., 2013)

2. Theoretical framing

Our entry point into creating this difference is mainly theoretically-inspired. We draw on feminist new materialisms as a pertinent lens and approach for undertaking a relational type of literature review. This theory acknowledges the agency of matter, decentralizes the human, and thereby enables us to understand in a new way the relationships between humans and machines in human enhancement, and to critically consider the human-centric assumptions of many human enhancement typologies. We specifically use the concept *relationality* as guiding thread to make sense of human enhancement in its complexity and get insights into its societal implications, from a sociological perspective. We ask questions such as, what is the relationship that is created between humans and machines? What relationships are modified or destroyed when we engage in human enhancement as a practice? What does a relational typology look like?

This theoretical framework in turn informed our choice of methods. On the one hand, feminist new materialisms encourage the use of diffractive reading as a method to reveal the researcher's positionality and methods, and account for the situated knowledges that are produced both in the articles selected in the review and by the reviewers themselves (Lazar et al., 2021) (van der Tuin, 2016). To best account for this situatedness and relationality of relational systematicity and of the results that we aim to produce, we argue that acknowledging our positionality (Haraway, 1988) and response-ability³ (Barad, 2007) as researcher and reviewer is crucial. As Van Even says in her doctoral dissertation about research dissemination: "Awareness of the provenance of our insights and the fact that a different decision path could lead to different insights, is important. Acknowledging this necessitates us to leave an openness in the framework, so that knowledge can remain something dynamic and fluid that keeps meandering along future lines. It prevents the framework (or any other, for that matter) from being perceived and used as something fixed or static. Instead, it invites others to pick up on one or more of the decision 'nodes' and chart their own path." (Van Even, 2023) To answer Van Even's call, we here shortly present our positionality as researchers. As white middle-class women from Belgium, the authors of this paper occupy a privileged position that might lead them to omit certain power dynamics at play in the definition of human enhancement and in their own review process. However, the first author's sociological background and strong interest in feminist and social justice concerns might help her pay a more acute attention to such issues and be critical toward the collected data. A last positional element that might influence the research results is that this research project aims at shifting the discourse on human enhancement from threat-based to opportunities-oriented and notably to try to highlight the emancipatory potential of human enhancement, whilst still considering the potential inequalities it might create or reproduce. It might encourage a rather optimistic conceptualization of human enhancement.

On the other hand, purposeful sampling provides an illustration of what diffractive reading might look like in a review process. It focuses on the identification of connections and dissonances; it allows to iteratively collect and analyze data while constantly questioning the selection process to most adequately understand a concept in its complexity (Benoot et al., 2016). By fostering this critical perspective on the selection process, it also represents a tool to support our response-ability as researcher: it encourages us to be transparent about the how and why certain worlds are made and not others, that is, to be clear about our inclusion criteria and the political or ideological ambitions we might have (Sauzet, 2021). This paper will present a worked example of how both components have been applied as part of our review methodology.

³In Barad's agential realism, we are always already in relation with each other, including with the world that is around us. We do not pre-exist these relations, neither do others or the world around us; we emerge through these relations, we are constituted by these relations. This means that in every relation, we are immediately responsible for the other that emerges at the same time as us, because we co-constitute it. We are required to directly be able to respond to the emergence of the other in the relation and their immediate dependence on us. That is why Barad talks of this responsibility as a response-ability.

Figure 1: Barad's brittlestar as an example of how purposefully sampling materializes in looking for evidence on the conceptualization of human enhancement in the literature

3. Purposeful Sampling: Privileging Fluidity Instead of a Priori Protocols

When we decided on conducting a scoping review on the concept human enhancement, more or less following Arksey and O'Malley's steps (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005), we anticipated that we would be entering an emergent field in which there would be little consensus on how to best define this phenomenon. Contrary to systematic reviews, scoping studies do not try to answer highly precise research questions but rather analyze broad concepts, without either selecting articles on basis of their study design or quality (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005).

Such as scoping review requires the scope of the sample to be wide (Sauzet, 2021). In an effort to make the review method fit the research objectives (Campbell et al., 2020), we used purposeful sampling to strategically navigate between the different ways of categorizing human enhancement, elaborating each time on insights gathered in relevant articles. This methodological choice aligns with the growing call of qualitative evidence reviewers for seeing literature reviews as interpretive rather than aggregative, implying that "in-depth synthesis of purposefully selected studies is more desirable than a superficial synthesis of a large number of studies" (Suri, 2011).

We relied on Barad's image of the brittlestar (Barad, 2014), that does not have a central brain but has a diffuse nervous system, implying that each of its arms can make decisions and move autonomously (Figure 1). In a similar way, each article we selected in this review opened to paths of interpretations of what human enhancement is, how to categorize it, and where to find conceptualizations of it. We followed each path through to its full implications while still leaving open the possibility to go back if we realized they were dead-ends. This aimed to serve as an alternative to the often linear, rigid and formalized selection process in systematic reviews, where the in- and exclusion criteria tend to restrict the variety of results and thus the richness of the understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Benoot et al., 2016). By contrast, our purposeful sampling is characterized by fluidity and openness.

Figure 1 presents a visual metaphor of the different paths we followed in our selection strategy - some of them are explained in more details below.

It is important to note that purposeful sampling is distinct from convenience sampling, as it necessitates the use of clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria (Stratton, 2024). We started by using broad keywords in different databases, looking specifically in the title. Here is an example of such search strategy (used in the Web of Science database): *TS=(“human enhancement” OR “human augmentation” OR “human improvement” OR “performance enhancement” OR bioenhancement) AND TS=(typolog* OR categoriz* OR classif* OR taxonomy OR framework)*. Our other inclusion criteria related to language (English, French, Dutch) and databases, although we left the option to also look elsewhere and include other sources, such as books and reports. The difference with a comprehensive search strategy is indeed that our in- and exclusion criteria served as general directives but did not seek to strictly restrict our sample; we stayed open at all times to following new paths that would enrich our understanding of human enhancement, whether it involved adding search terms, including other types of sources, or considering specific articles (see Figure 1). Rather than striving for comprehensiveness in the retrieval of studies for the review, we applied the criterion relevance of an article to bring clarity as the core parameter for inclusion (Atkinson et al., 2015).

Even before conducting a first search in a database, we gathered information where we knew that we could find it in its most relevant form – that is, in important articles on human enhancement that we had previously identified (Coyne, 1997). Starting from there, we then studied if there were existing concepts and categories linked to human enhancement that required to be included in our search strategy and we adapted our search terms accordingly. For example, we added “biohacking”, “body modification” and “bioenhancement” as synonyms for human enhancement after analyzing a few articles and operated a second retrieval of studies with these search terms.

This highlights one advantage of using purposeful sampling: it can allow to include cases that we know should absolutely be included and that would maybe not appear using a conventional search strategy (Campbell et al., 2020). This was the case for an article entitled “Towards an Operator 4.0 Typology: A Human-Centric Perspective on the Fourth Industrial Revolution Technologies” (Romero et al., 2016). Although it broadly addresses Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies and therefore did not include any of our keywords related to human augmentation or enhancement, it nevertheless offers a particularly valuable approach to developing a typology of augmenting technologies and is highly influential in the field.

Similarly, we included two reports commissioned by the European Union (Coenen et al., 2009) (Jensen et al., 2018) and one from the UK Ministry of Defence (UK Ministry of Defence, 2021) which constituted thorough scientific work but would not appear in scientific databases (see “reports” in Figure 1). One advantage of purposeful sampling is indeed the flexibility it offers to adapt our search strategy along the study. The lack of flexibility of systematic reviews’ *a priori* protocols would not fit the study of such an emergent field of study characterized by a lack of conceptual consensus (Coemans et al., 2015).

4. Diffractive Reading: Performing Human Enhancement as an Object of Knowledge

4.1. Barad’s Onto-Epistemology

Diffractive reading is a technique that acknowledges the entanglement of phenomena and their emergence as a material-discursive practice of boundary-making, notably in research, and relies on the action of “reading insights through one another” (Barad, 2007). In this research project, and through our feminist new materialist lens, we consider human enhancement as an object of knowledge that emerges through the intra-action of researchers and their research process, in line with Barad’s onto-epistemology (Barad, 2007). This has two implications. Firstly, it means that understanding the phenomenon human enhancement requires to critically read the literature and try to identify the assumptions, divergences and tensions that constitute it as an object of knowledge. We study in that way the boundary-making

Figure 2: A strategy for diffractive reading inspired by Sauzet (Sauzet, 2021)

practices that occur when defining and especially categorizing the phenomenon human enhancement. Secondly, this also means that the very process of gathering and analyzing these different publications in another publication similarly contributes to the emergence of human enhancement as an object of knowledge, and is thus agentic. Reviewing is “both the act of reviewing [and] enactments of the boundaries and properties of objects of knowledge” (Sauzet, 2021). As researchers, we thus take responsibility (or rather, response-ability) for the knowledge we produce and the way in which we produce it, taking into account the knowledges that are included and excluded. Additionally, this also means that we account for the situated knowledge that this paper represents (van der Tuin, 2016).

Diffractive reading is particularly adapted to the multi-disciplinarity of the field of human enhancement, as it “yields understandings of how different approaches within and across disciplines materialize and matter.” (Lazar et al., 2021) The concept of diffraction in physics indeed refers to how (light) waves bend or spread when passing through an opening or by an obstacle. The combination of the size of the opening and the wavelength defines the way in which the waves will appear on the other side of the opening or obstacle. Therefore, by analyzing the way in which the waves are diffracted, we can understand characteristics of the opening or obstacle itself. We can compare the (light) waves to knowledge about human enhancement and the opening or obstacle as the different perspectives taken to produce this knowledge. A diffractive reading of the literature on human enhancement can then provide insights into the assumptions and methodologies underlying the ways human enhancement is categorized.

4.2. An Example of How to Apply Diffractive Reading to Literature Reviews

After collecting our first publications, we created an Excel spreadsheet to chart the data (Arksey and O’Malley, 2005). Data collection and data analysis happened in a rather simultaneous way, with back-and-forth-movements from the one to the other, in a dynamic mixing inductive and deductive work. Our approach is akin to grounded theory methodologies because our goal is theory building (in the form of a typology). A theory emerges from the data and once it has emerged, the data is systematically collected and analyzed in regards to this emerging theory (Charmaz, 2001). We drew inspiration from Sauzet’s analytical strategy to diffractively read the publications we gathered (Sauzet, 2021); our strategy is visually represented in Figure 2.

On the one hand, we identified “which central agents are re-iteratively enacted in the publications as

Table 1

Concepts Used as Analytical Tools to Identify Dominant Assumptions in the Literature and Imagine Other Approaches

Inductive Concepts	Sensitizing Concepts
View on human enhancement	Societal/ethical issues considered
View on humans/technology/human-technology interaction	Decentralization of the human
Target technology	Capacities
Phase of technology	Emergence
Categories of human enhancement	Affects
Criterion for distinction across types	Intra-action
Other criteria discussed	Situated knowledges
Goal of human enhancement	Subjectivity

important for the object of knowledge” (Sauzet, 2021), that is, we identified what factors or phenomena are considered important to define and categorize human enhancement in the literature. We here found factors such as the type and role of technology involved in human enhancement, the criteria that can allow to distinguish across types of human enhancement, the stated goal of human enhancement, the author’s more or less critical attitude toward it, ...

On the other hand, we used these different “central agents” to analyze the statements that each publication made on these factors and identify potential tensions and divergences. Sauzet proposes the following question to guide the analysis: “How does the object of knowledge emerge as ex-tended between opposite, sometimes mutually incompatible statements in the literature?” (Sauzet, 2021). This allows to problematize and perform the emergence of human enhancement as an object of knowledge in the literature, as an *assemblage* made of different – and sometimes clashing – material-discursive practices. In our onto-epistemological approach, as stated earlier, we consider that gathering what we *know* about human enhancement simultaneously gives form to what human enhancement *is*.

Therefore, after the initial selection of an article, we collected descriptive data on the title, names of authors, date of publication, field, conceptualization and categorization of human enhancement. We then read them in-depth with a particular attention to the “central agents” that are considered important to categorize human enhancement. Whenever a factor was identified, other already read articles were analyzed once more to see how they position themselves on this factor. This led to an iterative construction of our analytical grid (Table 1) and a deepening of our understanding of the selected articles and the dialogue between them. Aside from the “central agents” inductively identified in the articles, we also read the articles through our feminist new materialist theoretical lens. Therefore, we inductively added some concepts to our analytical grid, such as “relationality”, “affects”, “intra-action”, ... This analysis of the divergence between typologies of human enhancement in the literature and the identification of their underlying assumptions, allowed us to then create our own typology based on different assumptions, a relational typology. We will be able to attain saturation if the selected sources provide enough information to produce our typology. This means that the creation of the typology already started after we analyzed the first collected articles, and that data collection and analysis will continue until we have produced a fully-fledged typology.

5. Proposing a Relational Typology of Human Enhancement

This paper allows to bring some first answers to the research questions guiding our scoping review. Our research question was, “What is the impact of applying relational systematicity to a review and how does it influence the presentation of the findings on the evidence investigated?” We also asked how a diffractive approach of reading primary studies to make sense of human enhancement practices and discourses might generate alternative, non-binary typologies that account for the intra-action of bodies, technologies, and environments.

To answer this latter question, our first results suggest that there are contradictions between the

assumptions underpinning the conceptualization and categorization of human enhancement present in existing typologies of human enhancement and how we conceptualized it using purposeful sampling and diffractive reading. The analytical grid presented in Table 1 for example allowed us to identify different ways of viewing human-enhancement interaction, in a more or less relational way, and different ways of defining the goal of human enhancement. For example, some articles handle technology as a mere tool, whereas others come closer to acknowledging its material agency and the active transformative force it can represent in our environment; some authors hold a very human-centric vision of human enhancement where technology is seen as created by humans to answer humans' needs, while (very rare) others envisage ways to create reciprocal human-technology relationships.

The lack of the latter type of conceptualizations suggests that our feminist post materialist approach is needed to produce an alternative typology that decenters the human and recognizes the importance of acknowledging the material agency of technology when conceptualizing human enhancement. Thanks to this theoretical frame and our relational approach to systematicity, our scoping review further highlights the situatedness of human enhancement and the embeddedness of human-technology relationships in a specific context. For instance, it allows us to situate the contemporary urge to self-optimization that sustains human enhancement as a practice in its broader neoliberal context, while also acknowledging the possibility of other kinds of motivations such as self-experimentation, playfulness and creativity (Rifai, 2022)(Teunisse et al., 2019).

Rather than resolving these tensions by trying to reduce them to a binary model, our diffractive approach foregrounds them. In our gathering of human enhancement typologies, we indeed identified a majority of binary models that take the form of matrices or rigid tables. Although their producers most of the time pretend that the boundaries between categories are not rigid and that they might sometimes overlap, we believe that this is not accurately represented in the visual typologies that they create. We further highlighted throughout this paper how research praxis is unpredictable and in constant evolution. Therefore, our diffractive approach suggests that a *fluid* typology of human enhancement might be the most appropriate means to create a common lexicon that acknowledges the intertwinement of the multiple layers that constitute this phenomenon as well as the uncertainty and instability of research praxis. This fluidity aims at counterbalancing the linearity and fixity of typologies and other models that impose their structure on readers and that simplify reality to make it understandable. Instead, we will build a fluid typology that accounts for the complexity of reality in a dynamic *assemblage* and that, as Van Even suggests, invites others to "chart their own path" into understanding and acting in this reality (Van Even, 2023). That requires the typology to be fluid, situated, and responsive to the material-discursive conditions that help produce it.

Figure 3 represents a draft version of our typology of human enhancement, inspired by Seebruck's typology of hackers and their motivations (Seebruck, 2015). The words between brackets around the circle refer to the different reasons why individuals decide to pursue human enhancement, their purposes, based on our first analysis of the literature. There is efficiency, self-experimentation, playfulness, automation and enhancement. The colored lines are associated with various types of enhanced humans that pursue these different purposes to varied levels. This is thus a typology in development, based only on preliminary results. However, it already shows what a fluid typology can look like. There are for example no clear boundaries between the categories, as the lines of color cross the lines that delineate the different motives of human enhancement. Furthermore, in Figure 3, the arrows pointing towards the outside of the circle suggest that the model is not closed on itself but open to its environment and that it can be further expanded if there are developments in the field under investigation. This aligns with the situatedness and embeddedness of phenomena in their context such as emphasized by feminist new materialisms.

Our sampling strategy has its flaws. We might have missed some interesting and important conceptualizations of human enhancement. However, the value of our relational systematism is that it has pushed us to remain at all times aware and clear about our decisions in the selection process and to remain open for human-machine configurations yet to (be)come. By being rigorous and transparent in our use of the chosen methodology, we aim to make our results (or at least our methods) applicable to other contexts, not for the purpose of trying to generalize them beyond the theoretical and conceptual

Figure 3: Fluid typology of human enhancement (work in progress) inspired by Seebruck's typology of hackers (Seebruck, 2015)

boundaries we have drawn for ourselves in conducting this review, but to achieve a level of methodological transferability across review projects and provide suggestions on how reviews on emerging fields and topics can potentially be approached methodologically.

We redefined systematicity as fluid, processual, situated and entangled and the product of this review will similarly be open-ended, non-linear and embedded in its context, which is what our first attempt at a typology aims to reflect (Figure 3). We believe that the case under analysis here showed that fluidity in the research process can sometimes be more appropriate than *a priori* rigid protocols to create an understanding of a phenomenon that reflects its multi-layered and constantly evolving complexity. We further believe this review to represent a solid contribution to the field of human enhancement because our approach allowed us to disentangle the assumptions underlying the conceptualization of human enhancement and to create a common lexicon that scholars across disciplines can critically use.

We believe that the form of literature review in development presented in this paper will inspire others to apprehend this research method with a more critical and relational approach, acknowledging the positionality and response-ability of the researchers who produced the papers that reviewers select as well as their own.

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Declaration on Generative AI

The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

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